

THE EFFICACY OF INDIVIDUAL WORK IN CULTIVATING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE AMONG PROSPECTIVE ECONOMISTS

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Abstract. *The modernization of education delineates its primary objectives: the cultivation of adept personnel possessing requisite qualifications and specialization; individuals who are competitive within the labor market, proficient, accountable, and adept in their respective professions; individuals oriented toward cognate spheres of activity; capable of efficacious engagement within their specialties at a global standard; and predisposed to perpetual professional advancement and social-professional mobility. This article expounds upon the efficacy of self-directed study in shaping the professional competence of prospective economists.*

Keywords: *professional competence, educational and pedagogical process, innovative activity, individual work, independent work.*

Amidst the ongoing educational reforms, significant societal shifts have transpired in conceptualizing educational objectives, recalibrating value systems, and fostering innovative collaborations between educators and students in both academic and extracurricular pursuits. Moreover, there has been a notable emphasis on the self-organization of student activities within specific domains. The overarching objective of higher education is now the cultivation of a creative individual equipped for autonomous development and innovative engagement. This transformation is facilitated through dynamic educational approaches, particularly interactive and collaborative methods involving close cooperation between educators and students [1].

The imperative lies in transitioning students from a passive role as mere recipients of knowledge and skills to the status of proactive contributors. Simultaneously, self-directed progress stands as a crucial prerequisite for instilling professional attributes in undergraduates. Central to this educational paradigm is the integration of independent or solitary research endeavors into the academic framework. The overarching objective of incorporating student-driven independent work within university education is to cultivate an engaged, self-reliant persona adept at applying acquired knowledge creatively in their professional pursuits.

In the contemporary landscape of production planning and organization, a university graduate's competence hinges on possessing profound knowledge and a robust foundation in mathematics. Such proficiency is deemed indispensable for one's readiness to navigate modern life and work effectively. A graduate is expected to exhibit well-developed mathematical thinking and master analytical and synthetic methods at a notably advanced professional level. To instill professionally significant knowledge, skills, and abilities, especially in economics, it is imperative to employ applied tasks throughout the teaching process. Notably, our teaching experience underscores that first-year students commonly encounter computational challenges and lack experience in utilizing mathematical tools for interpreting concepts, forecasting, optimization, and solving applied problems. Addressing these issues necessitates the incorporation of applied problems with elements of mathematical modeling and independent research work at the conclusion of each economics section. To optimize outcomes, engaging students in challenging homework, requiring significant time investment, personal computing resources, and

supplementary literature, is crucial. Offering tasks for consolidation and independent completion reinforces the learning process. To foster a thirst for knowledge and stimulate interest, task complexity should incrementally rise, adhering to didactic learning principles and focusing on developing professional qualities. It is noteworthy that the dynamics between teacher and student shift during independent work, with teachers assuming more advisory and motivational roles. This approach aims to stimulate the professional growth, creative activity, and initiative of bachelor students, empowering them to become active participants in their educational journey [3]. An examination of work programs and standards for the mathematical training of bachelors reveals a reduction in the labor intensity of academic disciplines. Concurrently, the time allocated for independent work has expanded, constituting more than half of the total teaching load. Despite the benefits, the substantial volume of independent work stipulated by the new education system poses considerable challenges.

The organization of independent work, aimed at cultivating professional qualities, necessitates careful planning and execution. The teacher orchestrates student activities both within and outside the classroom, fostering self-regulation and a genuine inclination for engaging in autonomous endeavors. This approach instills new attitudes toward the educational process, ensuring the comprehensive development of knowledge, skills, and abilities. In the study of economics, the primary facets of independent work encompass acquiring the informative component of educational content, cultivating the experience of self-directed learning, and enhancing autonomy in monitoring knowledge acquisition [1].

At every developmental stage, the planning of a student's independent work should adhere to a progression from simplicity to complexity. Evaluation of all independent tasks within the realm of economics education should be conducted using established criteria. An individualized approach is essential when organizing independent work—some students may require detailed guidance, others benefit from insights into potential challenges, while some can independently navigate problem-solving. Through the resolution of tasks during independent work, mental work skills are honed, information is assimilated, and previously studied material is reinforced [2].

Diverse forms of student independent work contribute significantly to heightened cognitive engagement and autonomy, crucial elements in preparing students for self-directed learning. Collaborative independent work, especially within team projects, underscores the effectiveness of teamwork in achieving educational objectives. To enhance outcomes, providing comprehensive educational materials, such as electronic lecture courses, solved standard problems, and self-study questions, is imperative [1].

Facilitating independent work involves creating an environment for exploration through a series of questions. These questions guide students to identify the pertinent area of economics for problem-solving and prompt consideration of additional data requirements. By systematically analyzing these questions, including those posed by students, a typology of potential issues in educational research can be developed. Encouraging students to formulate problems related to their future profession and solve them independently is particularly beneficial for fostering professional qualities [2].

We assert that successful outcomes in independent work as an instructional method hinge on students possessing sufficient skills, essential abilities, organizational aptitude, and a propensity for self-discipline. Throughout their training, future specialists must cultivate creative and research capabilities to effectively apply acquired knowledge in evolving professional landscapes. The

structuring of academic and extracurricular activities should emphasize developing the ability to learn, forming professional skills, and creatively applying knowledge in dynamic professional settings. The incentivizing role of independent work is evident in conferring professional acceleration to the learning process. This acceleration is manifested in students developing a vision for personal and professional growth, fostering a desire to attain those objectives. A multi-level approach to training necessitates tailoring independent work to individual student capabilities and demands the creation of comprehensive methodological support.

In conclusion, the significance of independent work in the educational landscape is paramount, serving as a catalyst for heightened cognitive activity, autonomy, and the development of professional qualities among students. The incorporation of diverse forms of independent work, whether undertaken individually or collaboratively within teams, underscores its efficacy in preparing students for self-directed learning and future professional endeavors. The structured planning of independent work, encompassing a progression from simpler to more complex tasks, ensures a comprehensive and gradual development of students' skills and abilities. The provision of educational materials and the encouragement of problem formulation related to future professions further enhance the effectiveness of independent work. As the educational paradigm evolves, the role of independent work becomes even more critical in fostering creative and research abilities, aligning students with the dynamic demands of their respective fields. In this context, the stimulating function of independent work emerges as a key driver, propelling students toward personal and professional growth, imbuing the learning process with purpose, and preparing them for the multifaceted challenges of their chosen professions.

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